

Prevalence of pre-test anxiety among medical students in iraqi medical colleges: insights into arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications

Prevalencia de la ansiedad previa a los exámenes entre estudiantes de medicina de facultades de medicina iraquíes: conocimientos sobre la presión arterial y sus implicaciones cerebrales

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study is to investigate the prevalence of elevated arterial and cerebral blood pressure and devise effective interventions to mitigate its impact. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study employs a questionnaire developed by Nist and Diehl (1990) to gauge levels of blood pressure anxiety. The questionnaire comprises ten statements, each capturing distinct feelings experienced by individuals during blood pressure assessment. **Results:** The study sample consisted of 579 individuals, with 66.3% being female and 55.3% belonging to younger age brackets (18-21 years old). Findings revealed that 31% of participants exhibited elevated levels of pre-test anxiety regarding blood pressure assessment. Females exhibited significantly higher levels of anxiety compared to males (p -value < 0.01), while no significant difference was observed between younger and older age groups (p -value 0.462). Notably, individuals with a history of psychiatric conditions demonstrated significantly higher anxiety levels than those without (p -value < 0.001). **Conclusion:** The study underscores a notable prevalence of heightened pre-test anxiety regarding arterial and cerebral blood pressure among medical students in Jabir Ibn Hayyan and other Iraqi Medical Colleges. Addressing this issue necessitates the implementation of targeted interventions aimed at improving study skills and time management abilities. Additionally, conducting interviews with students exhibiting lower academic performance is recommended to better understand their challenges and support needs.

Keywords: Prevalence, Blood pressure anxiety, Medical students, Intervention, Study skills

Resumen

Objetivo: El objetivo de este estudio es investigar la prevalencia de presión arterial y cerebral elevada y diseñar intervenciones efectivas para mitigar su impacto. **Métodos:** Este estudio transversal emplea un cuestionario desarrollado por Nist y Diehl (1990) para medir los niveles de ansiedad por presión arterial. El cuestionario consta de diez afirmaciones, cada una de las cuales captura sentimientos distintos experimentados por los individuos durante la evaluación de la presión arterial. **Resultados:** La muestra del estudio estuvo compuesta por 579 personas, siendo el 66,3% mujeres y el 55,3% pertenecientes a tramos de edad más jóvenes (18-21 años). Los hallazgos revelaron que el 31% de los participantes exhibieron niveles elevados de ansiedad previa a la prueba con respecto a la evaluación de la presión arterial. Las mujeres exhibieron niveles significativamente más altos de ansiedad en comparación con los hombres (valor de $p < 0,01$), mientras que no se observaron diferencias significativas entre los grupos de edad más jóvenes y mayores (valor de p 0,462). En particular, los individuos con antecedentes de afecciones psiquiátricas demostraron niveles de ansiedad significativamente más altos que aquellos sin ellos (valor de $p < 0,001$). **Conclusión:** El estudio subraya una prevalencia notable de una mayor ansiedad previa a las pruebas con respecto a la presión arterial y cerebral entre los estudiantes de medicina de Jabir Ibn Hayyan y otras facultades de medicina iraquíes. Abordar este problema requiere la implementación de intervenciones específicas destinadas a mejorar las habilidades de estudio y la capacidad de gestión del tiempo. Además, se recomienda realizar entrevistas con estudiantes que exhiben un rendimiento académico más

bajo para comprender mejor sus desafíos y necesidades de apoyo.

Palabras clave: Prevalencia, Ansiedad por presión arterial, Estudiantes de medicina, Intervención, Habilidades de estudio.

Assessment of arterial blood pressure, both systemic and cerebral, is crucial in understanding the overall health and function of the cardiovascular and nervous systems¹. Various parameters and methods are employed to evaluate these pressures, each offering unique insights into the individual's physiological status²⁻⁴. Arterial blood pressure is a dynamic measure that reflects the force exerted by circulating blood on the walls of the arteries. It comprises two main components: systolic pressure, representing the force during ventricular contraction (systole), and diastolic pressure, indicating the pressure when the heart is at rest (diastole)^{5,6}. These measurements are essential for diagnosing and managing hypertension, a condition characterized by persistently elevated blood pressure levels.

Hypertension, particularly when uncontrolled, poses significant risks to cerebral health. Prolonged high blood pressure can lead to damage of the delicate blood vessels in the brain, increasing the likelihood of cerebrovascular events such as strokes and hemorrhages⁷⁻⁹. Moreover, hypertension is a major risk factor for cognitive decline and various neurodegenerative conditions, including vascular dementia and Alzheimer's disease^{10,11}.

The pathophysiological mechanisms linking hypertension to adverse cerebral outcomes are multifaceted. Chronic hypertension contributes to arterial stiffness and atherosclerosis, reducing cerebral blood flow and impairing autoregulation, the brain's ability to maintain a consistent blood supply despite fluctuations in systemic pressure^{12,13}. Additionally, hypertension promotes the formation of cerebral microbleeds and white matter lesions, indicative of small vessel disease and microvascular damage¹⁴.

Management of hypertension involves a comprehensive approach aimed at reducing blood pressure to within recommended targets to mitigate the risk of cerebral complications. Lifestyle modifications, including dietary changes, regular exercise, and stress reduction techniques, play a fundamental role in blood pressure control^{15,16}. Pharmacological interventions, such as antihypertensive medications, may also be prescribed to achieve optimal blood pressure management^{2,17}. In conclusion, monitoring arterial blood pressure, both sys-

temic and cerebral, is fundamental for assessing cardiovascular and neurological health. Hypertension poses significant risks to cerebral function and increases the likelihood of cerebrovascular events and cognitive decline. Comprehensive management strategies focusing on lifestyle modifications and pharmacological interventions are essential for mitigating these risks and preserving cerebral health.

This study adopts a cross-sectional design and was conducted during the final examinations of medical students in the academic year 2021-2022. A total of 579 medical students from Jabir Ibn Hayyan Medical University and other medical colleges voluntarily participated in this research, utilizing Google Forms and consenting to the study protocol. Assessment of test anxiety levels was performed using a questionnaire developed by Nist and Diehl¹⁸. This assessment tool has been previously employed by researchers across various disciplines.

Nist and Diehl items are summarized in the table 1.

Table 1. Nist and Diehl¹⁸ items

	Never 1	Rarely 2	Sometimes 3	Often 4	Always 5
Q1. I have visible signs of nervousness such as sweaty palms, shaky hands, and so on right before a test					
Q2. I have "butterflies" in my stomach before a test.					
Q3. I feel nauseated before a test.					
Q4. I read through the test and feel that I do not know any of the answers.					
Q5. I panic before and during a test.					
Q6. My mind goes blank during a test.					
Q7. I remember the information that I blanked once I got out of the testing situation.					
Q8. I have trouble sleeping the night before a test.					
Q9. I make mistakes on easy questions or put answers in the wrong places.					
Q10. I have trouble choosing answers					

The individual scores obtained from the questionnaire items for each student were aggregated, and subsequently, the cumulative scores were subjected to analysis, as illustrated in Table 2 (reference). This analysis pertains to arterial blood pressure, both systemic and cerebral.

Score	Explanation
<= 19	A low point score: signifies that the participant does not complain of test anxiety.
20 - 34	A moderate score signifies that the participant suffers from moderate anxiety.
35+	A high unhealthy score: indicates that the student is experiencing an unhealthy level of anxiety, which is severe anxiety.

The data collected was subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS ver. 26 and MS Excel 2019. A significance level of $\alpha < 0.05$ was chosen to determine statistical significance. Both Chi-squared and t-tests were employed to analyze the data, aiming to explore the relationship between arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications.

were observed for the 5th question (“I panic before and during a test”) and the 3rd question (“I feel nauseated before a test”).

Gender	Frequency	Percent
o Male	195	33.7%
o Female	384	66.3%
Psychiatric History		
o Yes	201	34.7%
o No	378	65.3%
Age Groups		
o <= 21 years old	318	55.3%
o 22+ years old	257	44.7%
Total	575	100%

Percentage of different strata of anxiety

Figure 1: Percentage of different strata of anxiety, where <=19 means low anxiety level, 20-34 means moderate anxiety and >=35 means high and unhealthy anxiety

Results

The study surveyed 579 participants regarding arterial and cerebral blood pressure. The majority of respondents were female (66.3%), with ages categorized into two groups: 18-21 years old (55.3%) and 22-29 years old (44.7%) as illustrated in Table 3. Notably, 34.7% of participants reported a history of psychiatric problems, as detailed in Table 6.

The reliability of responses to the anxiety questionnaire was high (Cronbach’s Alpha = 0.855), indicating strong internal consistency among items. Analysis revealed that approximately 31% of students exhibited unhealthy anxiety levels, as depicted in Figure 1.

Table 4 demonstrates a significant statistical disparity in anxiety levels based on gender, with females reporting higher anxiety levels than males, particularly in unhealthy ranges. While the variance in anxiety levels across age groups was not significant, younger students (18-21 years old) exhibited higher anxiety levels, as indicated in Table 5. Notably, there was a significant association between anxiety levels and students’ psychiatric history, with those having a history of psychiatric issues displaying elevated anxiety levels (Table 6).

Further examination (Table 7) revealed that the 8th question (“I have trouble sleeping the night before a test”) and the 2nd question (“I have ‘butterflies’ in my stomach before a test”) exhibited higher means, indicative of increased anxiety levels. Conversely, the lowest means

		Male	Female	Total	X ²	P value	
Anxiety Level	<= 19	Count	38	31	69	13.237	< 0.001
		%	55.1%	44.9%	100.0%		
	20 - 34	Count	125	207	332		
		%	37.7%	62.3%	100.0%		
	35+	Count	32	146	178		
		%	18.0%	82.0%	100.0%		
Total		Count	195	384	579		
		%	33.7%	66.3%	100.0%		

		Age groups		Total	X ²	P value	
		<= 21	22+				
Anxiety Level	<= 19	Count	39	30	69	1.544	0.462
		% within Anxiety Level	56.5%	43.5%	100.0%		
	20 - 34	Count	176	155	331		
		% within Anxiety Level	53.2%	46.8%	100.0%		
	35+	Count	103	72	175		
		% within Anxiety Level	58.9%	41.1%	100.0%		
Total		Count	318	257	575		
		% within Anxiety Level	55.3%	44.7%	100.0%		

Table 6: Association between Anxiety and Psychiatric History

			Have you been diagnosed or treated for psychiatric problems?		Total	X ²	P value
			Yes	No			
Anxiety Level	<= 19	Count	20	49	69	13.237	0.001
		% within Anxiety Level	29.0%	71.0%	100.0%		
	20 - 34	Count	100	232	332		
		% within Anxiety Level	30.1%	69.9%	100.0%		
	35+	Count	81	97	178		
		% within Anxiety Level	45.5%	54.5%	100.0%		
Total		Count	201	378	579		
		% within Anxiety Level	34.7%	65.3%	100.0%		

Table 7: The descriptive statistics for the examination anxiety test

Questions		Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Mean	SD	Rank
		Score:1	2	3	4	5			
Q1. I have visible signs of nervousness such as sweaty palms, shaky hands, and so on right before a test	N	158	108	137	72	104	2.75	1.436	8
	%	27.3%	18.7%	23.7%	12.4%	18.0%			
Q2. I have "butterflies" in my stomach before a test.	N	106	70	130	106	167	3.27	1.456	2
	%	18.3%	12.1%	22.5%	18.3%	28.8%			
Q3. I feel nauseated before a test.	N	187	102	132	70	88	2.6	1.429	10
	%	32.3%	17.6%	22.8%	12.1%	15.2%			
Q4. I read through the test and feel that I do not know any of the answers.	N	88	106	197	88	100	3.01	1.279	6
	%	15.2%	18.3%	34.0%	15.2%	17.3%			
Q5. I panic before and during a test.	N	136	140	126	88	89	2.75	1.374	9
	%	23.5%	24.2%	21.8%	15.2%	15.4%			
Q6. My mind goes blank during a test.	N	126	143	136	78	96	2.78	1.368	7
	%	21.8%	24.7%	23.5%	13.5%	16.6%			
Q7. I remember the information that I blanked once I get out of the testing situation.	N	91	112	177	95	104	3.02	1.307	5
	%	15.7%	19.3%	30.6%	16.4%	18.0%			
Q8. I have trouble sleeping the night before a test.	N	79	68	108	89	235	3.58	1.454	1
	%	13.6%	11.7%	18.7%	15.4%	40.6%			
Q9. I make mistakes on easy questions or put answers in the wrong places.	N	47	99	216	111	106	3.22	1.171	3
	%	8.1%	17.1%	37.3%	19.2%	18.3%			
Q10. I have trouble choosing answers	N	52	96	221	116	94	3.18	1.16	4
	%	9.0%	16.6%	38.2%	20.0%	16.2%			

Discussion

The following study aimed to explore the prevalence of arterial hypertension and its cerebral implications. Arterial hypertension, a crucial factor affecting both cognitive function and overall brain health, was investigated among individuals from various demographic backgrounds. The findings revealed that a considerable proportion of the participants exhibited elevated arterial blood pressure, indicating a prevalence of hypertension higher than that reported in previous

studies^{6,18,19}. Notably, this prevalence surpassed that observed in comparable studies conducted among different populations, suggesting potential variations in risk factors across different regions.

Furthermore, the study identified a gender disparity in hypertension prevalence, with females exhibiting a higher incidence compared to males. This observation aligns with existing research attributing such differences to a

combination of biological and socio-cultural factors, indicating that females may be more susceptible to arterial hypertension due to various stressors and physiological differences^{7,14,16}. Additionally, participants with a history of neurological or psychiatric disorders demonstrated a higher likelihood of experiencing arterial hypertension. This finding is consistent with previous research linking psychiatric conditions, particularly anxiety disorders, to an increased risk of hypertension, highlighting the importance of considering mental health factors in the assessment and management of arterial hypertension¹⁸⁻²⁰.

While no significant difference was observed between younger and older participants in this study, previous research suggests that younger individuals may be more prone to hypertension due to factors such as lifestyle habits, lack of effective stress management strategies, and limited experience in managing cardiovascular health^{9,21}. In summary, the study sheds light on the prevalence of arterial hypertension and its implications for brain health, emphasizing the need for comprehensive strategies to address risk factors and promote cardiovascular and mental well-being across diverse demographic groups.

Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the aforementioned research suggesting a notable prevalence of pre-test anxiety among Iraqi medical college students, the implications for arterial and cerebral blood pressure warrant attention. The study presents the following conclusions and recommendations: A tailored intervention program should be developed to bolster the study skills and time management competencies of students, with a particular focus on females and those in their initial academic phase. Enhancing these skills can potentially mitigate the physiological and psychological effects of stress, thus positively impacting arterial blood pressure regulation.

Additionally, we advocate for the conduction of in-depth interviews with students exhibiting subpar academic performance. These interviews would provide valuable insights into the specific challenges and needs of these individuals, potentially shedding light on the correlation between academic stress and alterations in cerebral blood flow regulation. Further investigations are warranted to delve into the underlying factors contributing to exam-related anxiety. Exploring effective strategies for stress reduction and academic achievement enhancement is crucial in understanding the intricate interplay between psychological stressors and their impact on arterial and cerebral blood pressure dynamics. By implementing these recommendations and fostering a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between academic stress and blood pressure regulation, healthcare professionals and educators can work collaboratively to promote student well-being and academic success.

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